

Effect of Ignition Position on Vented Hydrogen-air Explosions

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Abstract

Among the factors affecting explosion venting, ignition position deserves more detailed investigation because it significantly affects the propagation of flame and the relief of internal pressure during a vented explosion. Explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratio ranging from 0.6 to 5.0 was experimentally investigated in the cases of back, central and front ignition. The results show that front ignition always leads to the minimum internal and external overpressure. Central ignition results in the maximum internal overpressure for all equivalence ratios and back ignition produces the maximum external overpressure for hydrogen-rich mixtures. Both the maximum internal and external overpressures first increase and then decrease with the increase of hydrogen equivalence ratio. The evolution of the external flame includes the formation of a fireball and a jet flame. The maximum lengths of the external flame are nearly identical when hydrogen-air mixtures are back and centrally ignited, which are larger than those in the front ignition case. For equivalence ratio of 3.0 and 5.0, the interaction of internal flame with the backward propagating pressure wave resulted from external explosion leads to the appearance of fine cellular structure and the oscillation of the internal pressure.

Keywords Hydrogen safety; Explosion venting; Ignition position; Flame propagation; Overpressure

1. Introduction

Explosion venting is an effective method to protect equipments, pipes and buildings against accidental internal gas explosions. The key problem in venting lies in the appropriate design of vent parameters for effective pressure relief and avoiding secondary disasters resulted from explosion venting. Among the factors affecting explosion venting, ignition position deserves special attention because it can not be correctly expected in real life.

Explosion venting in the case of different ignition positions has been experimentally and numerically investigated [1-6]. Generally, three ignition positions have been focused on, either at the center of the chamber (central ignition), near the vent (front ignition) or at the wall opposite to the vent (back ignition), and it has been found that a number of factors contribute to the effect of ignition position on the evolution of the internal overpressure after vent failure, such as flame instability, amount of unburned gases left inside the vessel and external explosion.

Special attention is paid to the effect of ignition position on the maximum internal overpressure in the previous investigations [7-14]. Bradley and Micheson [7] regarded central ignition in a spherical vented vessel as the worst case because of its maximum flame area and minimum heat loss from flame to vessel wall. Solberg et al. [8] found central ignition has the strongest pressure rise. In the presence of a vent duct, Ponizy and Leyer [9] found that central ignition and front ignition leads to the maximum and minimum internal overpressure, respectively. On the contrary, Kasmani et al. [10] found that more serious explosions are generated from an back ignition position rather than from central ignition position, because back ignition gives a greater distance for the flame to be accelerated. The experimental results of Ferrara et al. [11] also show that back ignition results in higher maximum overpressures than central ignition for methane-air mixtures but no monotonic behavior can be found for propane-air mixtures. No one worst ignition location for all cases tested

was observed by Bauwens et al. [12] due to the complex interplay of such competing factors as ignition position, vent size and obstacles; similarly, Rocourt et al.[13] found that central ignition generates maximal internal overpressure only for small vent areas.

The effect of ignition position on the external explosion has also been investigated [14-17]. It has been found that the external cloud reaches its maximum size in the case of back ignition, which leads to the highest overpressure of the external explosion. Front ignition produces negligible external explosion because only a very small quantity of unburned gas is expelled and ignited very early [14,15]. As a consequence, the amplitude of the internal pressure associated with the external explosion decreases with the decrease of the distance between the ignition position and the vent [5,12].

Given the former researches [1-17], some important aspects of explosion venting in the case of different ignition position have not been clear yet. For example, how much is the discrepancy of the maximum internal overpressures caused by different ignition position, and how does this discrepancy vary with other vent parameters such as fuel concentration? How does ignition position affect the external explosion evolution, and in which conditions can the external explosion affect significantly the internal pressure relief? In this paper, explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratio ranging from 0.6 to 5.0 was experimentally investigated in a vented cylindrical vessel in the case of back, central and front ignitions respectively to address the problems.

2. Experimental

Experiments were conducted in a stainless cylindrical vessel with necks at its waist, as shown in Fig.1. One exit of the vented vessel is sealed with a blind flange, and the other with a diaphragm (vent direction). Both inner diameter and length of the cylindrical vessel are 25cm. The size of neck's square cross section is 7cm×7cm, and the length of necks is 10cm. At both ends of the vessel, two

quartz windows with same 50mm thickness are mounted for allowing optical access necessary to the schlieren system. For each test, one of three ignition positions was used, either at the center of the neck opposite to vent direction (BI: back ignition), at the center of the vessel (CI: central ignition), or at the center of the neck along the vent direction (FI: front ignition). The ignition energy is kept about 500 mJ in every test. The initial pressure and temperature of hydrogen-air mixtures were 1 atm. and 280 K, respectively. Five hydrogen-air equivalence ratio (ϕ) of 0.6, 1.0, 1.6, 3.0 and 5.0 were taken into account.

Fig.1- Schematic of vented vessel. BI: back ignition, CI: central ignition, FI: front ignition.

Fig.2 presents a schematic of experimental layout. Schlieren system combined with high speed camera 1 was adopted to visualize the explosion flame in vessel. High speed camera 2 was used to record the explosion flame both inside and outside of the vessel. Frame rates of high-speed camera 1 and 2 were 10,000 fps and 5,000 fps, respectively. Three piezoelectric pressure transducers were employed to record pressure histories inside and outside of vessel during venting process: PT_1 was installed on the vessel wall opposite to vent, PT_2 was on the neck wall 2cm away from vent cover, and PT_3 was 35cm away from vent cover in outer space. The pressure transducers were all coated with a thin layer of silicon grease to avoid thermal effects on the pressure measurements.

Fig.2- Experimental layout.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Pressure profile in vessel

Typical pressure histories in vessel measured by PT₁ for different hydrogen equivalence ratio are shown in Fig.3. It is found that, both ignition position and hydrogen equivalence ratio have critical effect on internal pressure relief. Except $\phi=0.6$, the internal pressures continue to increase after vent failure to their peaks and then decrease in the case of back and central ignition, however two or three pressure peaks can be observed when the hydrogen-air mixtures are front ignited. For $\phi=0.6$, multi-peak pressure profiles with significant oscillation, resulted from the interaction between the internal combustion and the acoustic wave [1,2,13,18], can be observed independent of ignition positions.

Fig.3- Pressure profiles in the vessel.

Acoustic oscillation can also be observed for $\phi=1.0$ and 1.6 with much smaller oscillation amplitude in the case of front ignition. Experimental results show that the frequency of acoustic oscillation varies with hydrogen equivalence ratio. Fig.4 shows the details of pressure oscillations in vessel. The frequency of pressure oscillation is about $1600\sim 2000\text{Hz}$ for $\phi=0.6$ while it increases to $2000\sim 2500\text{Hz}$ for $\phi=1.6$. The oscillation frequency f_a can be estimated by $f_a = c/2L$ [19], where c is the sound speed in vessel, L is the length of enclosure. The sound speed of gas mixture increases with ϕ increasing from 0.6 to 1.6 , so the oscillation frequency also increases.

Fig.4- Expanded interval of acoustic oscillations. Front ignition.

It is worth noticing that pressure oscillation triggered by external explosion, as discovered by Harrison and Eyer [15], can also be observed under some suitable conditions in this paper. For example, the pressure oscillation in the cases of back and central ignitions for $\phi=3.0$ as shown in Fig.3, which will be discussed in detail in the following section.

Fig.5 summarizes the effect of ignition position and hydrogen equivalence ratio on the maximum overpressure in vessel (p_{red}). As expected, p_{red} exhibits sensitivity to both ignition position and equivalence ratio. p_{red} first increases and then decreases with ϕ increasing from 0.6 to 5.0, and moreover the discrepancies are small for too lean and too rich hydrogen-air mixtures because of their low burning rates.

Fig.5- Maximum overpressure in the vessel vs. hydrogen equivalence ratio.

For all equivalence ratios tested in current experiments, central ignition and front ignition lead to the maximum and minimum values of p_{red} , respectively. When the hydrogen-air mixtures are

front-ignited, flame propagates in the direction opposite to venting and therefore the flame was decelerated due to the quick venting of burned gas mixtures, which results in the minimum flame speed and the minimum p_{red} . As shown in Fig.6, the flame is pushed to the vent because the velocity of outflow exceeds the flame speed at the early stage after vent failure. On the contrary, in the cases of back and central ignitions, the flame is accelerated and stretched to the vent due to the gas flow in front of flame surface, and as a consequence, p_{red} is higher.

Fig.6- Schlieren images of the propagating internal flame. $\phi = 1.0$. BI: back ignition, CI: central ignition, FI: front ignition. t_b is the time of vent failure. Horizontal arrow denotes vent direction.

The reasons for the difference of p_{red} between the cases of central and back ignitions are as follows: first, the nearly spherical flame bubble in the case of central ignition has the largest flame area and then the fastest mass burning rate [1,9]; second, a large part of the flame contacts the vessel wall for back ignition as shown in Fig.6, which results in significant heat loss[1,20], but in the case of central ignition the heat loss is much reduced because the flame does not touch vessel wall until the final stage of venting; third, for central ignition, a larger amount of unburnt hydrogen-air mixtures left inside the vessel after vent failure [4,11,21].

3.2 Evolution of the external flame

In current experiments, the external flames can be observed for $\phi \geq 1.0$, and typical images of the

external flame are presented in Fig.7. It is easily observed that, a fireball with a diameter much larger than the length of vent side first appears in front of the vent and then it is distorted to become a jet structure. The latter extends quickly to its maximum length L_{\max} , then decreases in length and disappears lastly.

The evolution of external flame includes two stages: (1) Close to the vent exit, the combustion of the mushroom-like vented unburned mixtures leads to a nearly spherical fireball, which has been found especially for large vent areas [14,15,22]. Resultantly external explosion occurs as a consequence of its quick combustion. (2) The further combustion of residual hydrogen in the vented burnt mixtures results in the jet structures which can be regarded as the non-premixed flames.

Fig.7- Images of the external flame. $\phi = 3.0$. t is the start time of external flame.

In experiment it is also found that back ignition and front ignition lead to the maximum and minimum sizes of the fireball respectively. When the hydrogen-air mixtures are back-ignited, a largest amount of unburned gas mixtures are expelled outside of vessel to form a external combustible cloud [14], which is ignited by the subsequent flame. The external flame propagates quickly to form a largest fireball, as show in Fig.7. On the contrary, when the hydrogen-air mixtures are front-ignited, the burnt gases are vented at an early stage of the combustion and therefore it is

difficult to form the external combustible cloud [5], so the first stage (combustion of the vented unburned mixtures) is nearly absent. Experimental results also show that the size of the fireball increases with the hydrogen mixture increasing from stoichiometric to rich. One probable reason is that, it provides a longer time for more unburned hydrogen-air mixtures to be vented and form an external combustible cloud with larger volume, due to the decrease of burning rate with the increase of hydrogen equivalence ratio.

In addition, it is found that both ignition position and hydrogen equivalence ratio have critical effect on the maximum length of the external jet flame, which is summarized in Fig.8. It can be seen that, for all equivalence ratio tested in current experiments, the maximum lengths of the external jet flame are nearly equal for back and central ignitions. They are larger than that for front ignition.

Fig.8- Maximum external flame length vs. equivalence ratio.

As discussed above, the jet flames are due to the combustion of the vented burnt mixture involving residual hydrogen, so its maximum length may be closely related with the exit velocity of gas mixture (u) and the volume fraction of residual hydrogen in the vented gas mixture. When the hydrogen-air mixtures with the same concentration are ignited at different positions, the volume fractions of residual hydrogen in the vented burnt mixture are nearly identical, so the exit velocity of gas mixtures (u) determines the maximum length of the external flame. Furthermore u can be

calculated by $u = \sqrt{2\Delta p / \rho}$ [14], where Δp is the pressure difference at vent exit, ρ is the density of the vented gas mixture. In current study, Δp can be approximated as the overpressure measured by PT₂ which is mounted at the vent exit. It is found that the pressure profiles are similar in the cases of back and central ignitions, whose average amplitudes after vent failure are higher than that in the front ignition case, as typically shown in Fig.9. This may be one key reason to yield the difference in maximum length of the external flame.

Fig.9- Pressure profiles at vent exit measure by PT₂. $\phi = 1.0$.

If the hydrogen-air mixtures with varying equivalence ratio are ignited at the same position, the maximum length of the external jet flame increases with the increase of equivalence ratio, as shown in Fig.8. This should be attributed to the volume fraction of the residual hydrogen in the vented gas mixtures. It increases with the increase of the initial hydrogen-air equivalence ratio, so it takes a longer distance for the richer vented gas mixtures to be diluted and combusted. As a result, the maximum length of the external jet flame increases.

3.3 Pressure profile outside of vessel

Fig.10 presents typical pressure profiles outside of the vessel measured by the pressure transducer locating 35 cm away from vent exit (PT₃). Three pressure peaks p_1 , p_2 and p_3 can be obviously observed when the hydrogen-air mixtures are centrally ignited. The first pressure peak p_1 is about a few kilopascals, which is resulted from the burst of the vent cover. The second one p_2

and the third one p_3 correspond to the quick combustion of the external combustible cloud (external explosion) and the following jet of burned mixtures, respectively. It is found that p_2 has higher amplitude when $\phi \geq 1.6$, especially in the back ignition case. As shown in Fig.10, p_2 is significantly increased and dominates the pressure profile due to the turbulent external explosion. However, p_3 has slightly higher amplitude when $\phi \leq 1.0$.

The time interval between p_1 and p_2 is only a few milliseconds when the mixtures are back-ignited, but it significantly decays with the ignition position moved to the vent. This can be attributed to the fact that the flame surface gets nearer to the vent at the time of vent failure when ignition position approaches the vent, so it takes less time for the internal flame to rush out of the vent and trigger the external explosion. As a result, the pressure peaks can be hardly distinguished in the front ignition case, as shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10- Pressure profile outside of vessel. $\phi = 5.0$.

Fig.11 presents the maximum external overpressure p_{ext} as a function of equivalence ratio in the cases of three ignition positions. For all equivalence ratios currently tested, front ignition leads to the minimum external overpressure p_{ext} due to the weak external explosion. In the central ignition case, p_{ext} increases to its maximum with ϕ increasing from 0.6 to 1.6 and then decreases with ϕ increasing to 5.0. For back ignition, similar trend is observed with critical equivalence ratio of 3.0. It is interestingly noted that p_{ext} is nearly equal in the back and central ignition cases for $\phi \leq 1.0$, but

back ignition resulted in much higher p_{ext} for hydrogen rich mixtures due to the turbulent external explosion, especially for $\phi=3.0$.

Fig.11- Maximum external overpressure vs. equivalence ratio.

The explanation into the trend that p_{ext} first increases to their maximum values with ϕ and then decrease with the further increase of ϕ in the case of central and back ignition is as follows. When the hydrogen mixtures are initially rich, external explosion occurs and the resulted p_2 becomes the dominant pressure peak, and the amplitude of p_2 mainly depends on the volume, concentration and the ignition time of the combustible cloud formed in front of the vent. The burning rate in the vessel decreases with hydrogen concentration increasing from stoichiometric to rich. Consequently, more unburnt mixture is discharged and takes a longer time to be diluted to approach stoichiometric, so p_{ext} first increases with the increase of ϕ . But with a further increase of ϕ , although more unburned hydrogen is expelled, it is still too rich when ignited by the rushing-out internal flame and as a result p_{ext} decreases.

3.4 Effect of external explosion on internal pressure

The external explosion can affect the relief of the internal explosion pressure by means of backflow and the subsequent turbulization [11,23,24]. In current experiments, the effect of external explosion on internal pressure relief can be clearly observed only for $\phi=3.0$ and 5.0 in the case of back and central ignition.

Taking the back ignition case with $\phi = 5.0$ as an example, Fig.12 shows that an external pressure peak appears due to the external explosion, which exceeds the internal pressure. The explosion pressure wave propagates from outside into the vessel, and sequentially induces a pressure peak at PT₂ and another one at PT₁. The induced backflow in Fig.13 can provide further verification for this.

Fig.12- Pressure profile in and outside of vessel. $\phi = 5.0$. Back ignition.

Fig.13- Effect of backflow on internal flame. $\phi = 5.0$. Back ignition. t_b is the time of vent failure.

Horizontal arrow denotes vent direction.

As shown in Fig.12, oscillation of the internal pressure appears after the occurrence of the external explosion, which may be attributed to the interaction of internal flame with the backward-propagating pressure wave due to external explosion [23,24]. And a kind of cellular structure as shown in Fig.14, with much smaller cells than the spontaneous one, appears periodically on the smooth part of the flame surface nearly at the same time and at an equal frequency with internal pressure oscillation. In current experiment, the pressure wave induced cellular structure can only be clearly observed for $\phi = 5.0$ and 3.0, because it is covered by the spontaneous one which appears earlier and its size decreases with the decrease of hydrogen equivalence ratio.

Fig.14-Cellular structure on flame surface. $\phi = 5.0$. Back ignition.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, experiments on explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratio ϕ ranging from 0.6 to 5.0 were conducted to investigate the effect of three ignition positions on pressure profile and flame behavior inside and outside of cylindrical vessel. Acoustic oscillation of the internal pressure occurs for $\phi = 0.6$ at all three ignition positions, which can be also observed but with much smaller oscillation amplitude for $\phi = 1.0$ and 1.6 only in the case of front ignition. Central and front ignitions lead to the maximum and minimum internal overpressures respectively. This overpressure first increases with ϕ increasing to 1.6 and then decreases with a further increase of ϕ . The evolution of the external flame involves the formation of a fireball and the spread of a jet flame. The maximum lengths of the jet flame are nearly identical when the hydrogen-air mixtures are back and centrally ignited, which is larger than that in the front ignition case. Front ignition always leads to the minimum external overpressure, and back ignition leads to the maximum external overpressure for initially hydrogen rich mixtures. The maximum external overpressure in the back and central ignition case first increase and then decreases with the increase of ϕ but different critical value. For $\phi = 3.0$ and 5.0, the interaction of internal flame with the backward propagating pressure wave leads to the appearance of fine cellular structure and the oscillation of the internal pressure.

Acknowledgments

This study is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 51276177) and by EU HySEA project (No. 671461).

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